

Composition and Technology of Processing used Vehicle Tires and Obtaining Road Surfaces Base

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Abstract: This scientific article proposes the technology of recycling tires and obtaining an environmentally safe finished product. Modern methods of preparation of the product composition are explained using scientific principles. In this invention, the scientific significance and foreign experiences of obtaining a finished product from secondary tire scraps and the development of new composite road plates were studied, and the mechanisms of waste utilization were studied. Technological processes, new methods, ingredients are studied in the article.

Keywords: processes, utilization, interactive phosphogypsum, ingredients, industrial scale, carbomidoformaldehyde resins, reactor, polymers, synthetic rubber, petroleum.

1. Introduction

The processes of developing the technology of obtaining new road pavements that replace imports through the utilization of vehicle tires are represented. In addition, for the first time, technologies for preparing road pavements were developed by making a composition of tire shreds with interactive phosphogypsum. Given that the creation, operation and maintenance of road infrastructure requires a certain amount of capital, the scientific article on the technologies for the development of road surfaces using local secondary raw materials lists specific factors.

Modern methods of preparation of the product composition are explained using scientific principles. In this invention, the scientific significance and foreign experiences of obtaining a finished product from secondary tire scraps and the development of new composite road plates were studied, and the mechanisms of waste utilization were studied. A technology for obtaining finished products from secondary tire sawdust with a new composition has been developed. A mobile plant for the processing of vehicle tires and a new composition is proposed. Using local secondary waste of production, road pavement compositions are represented.

For the first time, the physico-chemical properties of the products of the processing of used vehicle tires and the preparation of road pavements based on them at the industrial level were determined, and a scientific guide was prepared. The effects of the components of the liquid composition and their physico-chemical parameters were proven using secondary tire sawdust.

With the help of secondary tire sawdust, the cold and heat resistance and operational properties of the liquid composition are determined, and the technical condition is developed. The

composition and technology of obtaining a liquid composition with the help of secondary tire sawdust is created, and proposals for the development of road surfaces on an industrial scale are developed.

2. Methodology

The total moisture content of phosphogypsum is up to 45%, therefore phosphogypsum was heated at a temperature of 1500C for 1 hour before use, crushed and reduced to a powder state and then used. As an additive, sand with a particle size of 0.2-0.25 mm is used. We created a new composite material by mixing PPK and fillers together and took samples by pouring them into molds.

Because it helps them to study their chemical and physical-mechanical properties.

Title of the invention: A method of developing road surfaces using secondary tire slag.

It was found that the developed interpolymer materials can be used as a blocking hydrogel and anti-filtration screen if there is an excess of KMTs-Na, and if there is an excess of KFS, it is possible to obtain porous materials with dispersed fillers.

If crude oil or a small amount of asphaltenes are used as additives when strengthening primers with carbomidoformaldehyde resins, the sequence of their addition is determined by the type of mechanisms used. Soils reinforced with organic binders, including phosphogypsum, lime and cement, should be compacted within 2 hours after mixing. If the air temperature is not less than 150 C, it is allowed to extend the time between mixing and compaction up to 4 hours. Compaction of soils reinforced with organic binding materials should be completed during the shift.

Figure 1. Working scheme of the technology of obtaining road surfaces for the road base using secondary tire sawdust and interactive phosphogypsum

Static description of the invention:

- 1-Main shredder (reactor) hole,
- 2- Reactor vibration separator and temperature measurement,
- 3- Thermal reactor, rotor magnetic separator,
- 4-Measuring transmitter, flywheel,
- 5-Magnetic separator that separates the metal part of tires,
- 6-Shredder for hard cutting (the process of turning tire sawdust into a dispersed medium),
- 7-Reactor for cross-linking of phosphogypsum with additional asphaltene substances
- 8-Thermal reactor hole
- 9-Reactor temperature measurement and control hole
- 10-Two-Roll Grinder (Ingredient Mixing Device)
- 11-Aggregate for ensuring interconnection of solid mass substances
- 12-Sampling tape
- 13-Rotary vibration separator (Ensures connection of components)
- 14-Finished product receiving hole

3. Results

Functional description of the invention: 1- Secondary tire sawdust is introduced from the hole of the main shredder (reactor) and 2- Reactor with the help of a vibrating separator and a temperature measuring device 3- Thermal reactor, the temperature of the rotor magnetic separator rises to 1200 So (melted up to 1 hour), 4- Measuring transmitter - the amount of raw materials is controlled through the flywheel and 5- It is separated from mechanical compounds using a magnetic separator that separates the metal part of the tires and 6- It is sent to the shredder for hard cutting (the process of turning tire sawdust into a dispersed medium), 7- Phosphogypsum cross-linking with additional asphaltene substances is monitored through the reactor and 8-Thermal reactor hole, every 30 minutes 9-Reactor temperature is measured and samples are taken through the control hole. 10-Two-roller grinder (Ingredient Mixing Device) is used to mix the components with heavy adhesion. 11-The solid mass is mixed by means of a cross-linking unit, and the quality of the product is controlled by 12-Sampling belt to check again.

Mixing of the mass is carried out through the device of 13-Rotary vibrating separator (ensures mixing of components). 14-Finished product receiving hole is taken ready road bed. In general, this process takes up to 2 hours in total.

Abstract of Invention.

4 Discussion

There is a permanent stock of secondary tires. Only 20% of their total number is recycled. Used tires are the largest production of waste products containing polymers that do not undergo natural decomposition. Therefore, recycling and recycling end-of-life tires are of great economic and environmental importance. The analysis of the scientific and technical level of the development of road surfaces using secondary tire scrap requires that the processing of rubber and similar materials is complicated.

The level of environmental safety is an important factor in this. One of the most common ways of tire recycling and technological decomposition is the pyrolysis method.

The advantage of tire recycling is that 80% of the world's tire supply is made from synthetic rubber, which is a non-renewable natural resource derived from petroleum. was determined and a scientific guide was prepared.

The effects of the components of the liquid composition and their physico-chemical parameters were proven using secondary tire sawdust.

IR-spectral analysis of rubber compounds in the composition of secondary tire sawdust and interactive phosphogypsum composition

According to the IR-spectrum analysis of the TsD-7 installation, 1464 cm⁻¹; 1383 cm⁻¹; and the vibrations corresponding to 724 cm⁻¹ were found to belong to sulfoxides related to the –CH₂–CH₃ group. This TsD-7 device was analyzed separately due to the fact that it was not clearly visible in the main spectrum due to the small amount in the composition of the tire sawdust.

With the help of secondary tire sawdust, the cold and heat resistance and operational properties of the liquid composition are determined, and the technical condition is developed. The composition and technology of obtaining a liquid composition with the help of secondary tire sawdust is created, and proposals for the development of road surfaces on an industrial scale are developed.

The physico-chemical properties of local raw materials and industrial products were determined for the processing of used vehicle tires and obtaining road pavements based on them;

The effects and physico-chemical parameters of the components of the processing of used vehicle tires and road pavements based on them have been proven;

Processing of used vehicle tires and determination of cold and heat resistance and operational properties of road surfaces based on them;

CONCLUSION

The composition and technology of processing used vehicle tires and obtaining road surfaces based on them was created. In addition, it was shown that it is possible to control the complex of physico-chemical properties of composite materials obtained on the basis of dispersed filler from asphaltene heavy hydrocarbon compounds.

It was found that the nature and amount of the filler added to the samples play an important role. A description of the effect of dispersed fillers on the heat resistance of KM was determined. It was shown that the specific interaction of the interpolymer matrix with the surface of the filler is a clear factor in increasing the thermal resistance of the filled materials, and at the same time, the stability of the thermal oxidation destruction.

The soil reinforced with an organic binder is compacted by passing 10-15 times over one track with a wheeled roller. Maintenance work on reinforced soils treated with bitumen emulsion or liquid bitumen cement is carried out by sprinkling bitumen emulsion at the rate of 0.6-0.8 dm³/m² on the layer in air temperature above 150 C and in the absence of precipitation. If the structural layer is laid on it within a day, there will be no need for maintenance work.

The formula of the invention

What does this device consist of ? It consists of the following components: 1-Main shredder (reactor) hole, 2-Reactor vibration separator and temperature measurement, 3- Thermal reactor, rotor magnetic separator, 4-Measuring transmitter, flywheel, 5-Magnetic separator that separates the metal part of tires, 6-Solid Shredder for cutting (the process of converting tire sawdust into a dispersed medium), 7-Reactor for cross-linking of phosphogypsum with additional asphaltene substances 8-Thermal reactor hole 9-Reactor temperature measurement and control hole, It is composed of 10-Two-roller grinder (Ingredient mixture making device), 11-Assembly of solid mass materials, 12-Sampling belt, 13-Rotary vibrating separator (Ensures the combination of components), 14-Finished product receiving hole , differs in the following: reactor devices for secondary tire slag and phosphogypsum, dispersed fillers are offered, and the technology of obtaining road pavements for road base with a new composition has been created.

References

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev, *Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan. Speech at the joint meeting of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the ceremonial inauguration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan* («Uzbekistan» NMIU, Tashkent, 2016)
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoev, *Ensuring the rule of law and human interests is the guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being. Speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan* («Uzbekistan» NMIU, Tashkent, 2016)
3. World sale of tires. (<http://www.tvre.com/report/paper.html?pubdate=19992F082F14&x=8&v=15>). Проверено 24.08.2003. 134
4. M.M. Mirsaidov, O.M. Dusmatov, M.U. Khodjabekov, *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, **282** (2022) https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10853-2_12
5. M.M. Mirsaidov, O.M. Dusmatov, M.U. Khodjabekov, *The problem of mathematical modeling of a vibration protected rod under kinematic excitations*, in IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering, **1030**, 012069 (2021) <https://doi:10.1088/1757-899X/1030/1/012069>
6. M.M. Mirsaidov, O.M. Dusmatov, M.U. Khodjabekov, *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, **170** (2021) https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79983-0_20
7. M.M. Mirsaidov, O.M. Dusmatov, M.U. Khodjabekov, *Stability of nonlinear vibrations of plate protected from vibrations*, in Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **1921**, 012097 (2021) <https://doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1921/1/012097>
8. M.M. Khafizov, Sh.M. Mirzиеv, *Effect of disperse fillers on the properties of interpolymer composite materials* (Kimè magazine of Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan, 1999)
9. M.M. Khafizov, Sh.M. Mirzиеv, *Initial patent*, **3** (1999)

10. Schonert. K. Chem. Ing. Technik. 43. №13. 1971. s. 773 777.
11. Bulman, S. Chem. Ing. Technik. 42. №5. 1970. s. 277 281.
12. Kautschuk. Gummi. Kunststoffe. 1995, v.48, №12, pp. 909-912. IQiait K.Carr S.H. Solid-State Pulverization: A New Polymer Processing and Power Technology Khait K.Carr S.H. Technomic Publishing Co., Lancaster-Basel, 2001, p.51. 133
13. Rapra Review Report Rapra Technology Ltd. 1997. 99. pp. 23
14. Reclaimed Rubber-are our technical abilities at the end by Klaus Knorr/Germany presented at tiie meeting of the Rubber Division, American Chemical Society Cleveland, Ohio. Rubber and Plastics News. 2,1996, v.XXVI, №1, p.
15. Scrap tires. TAB special report TAB. -1989. 1. p. 8 Terrel H. Oil in the sea; an international concern H. Terrel Ocean Ind. 1987. Vol. 22, 9. P. 102-
16. Tests show powder retrieves dispersing hydrocarbons in spill// Offshore. 1988, II.-V. 48, 2 P
17. Tires Wasser Boden Luft Umweltschutz -1997. 09 april. Weaver B. Scrap tires: where the rubber meets the road Weaver B. Pit and Quarry. 1994. 11. p.